

Sensitivity of bias correction step on generating hydrological scenarios

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ABSTRACT

Significant shifts in hydro-climatic regimes are expected in many parts of the world during the 21st century, affecting the water cycle. Vulnerability, impact, and adaptation studies often use tailored modeling chains to assess the expected effects of climate change, but the robustness of these chains is rarely investigated. This highlights the need for more rigorous evaluation of modeling chains to ensure that they are reliable for informed decision-making processes. To address this gap, we propose a framework for evaluating the sensitivity of hydrological scenario production to the bias correction step. We apply the framework to the Senegal River Basin, using three bias correction methods (linear scale, empirical quantile mapping, and nested bias correction) and three procedures (climate-correction, hydrological-correction, and climate-hydrological-correction). Our results show that the choice of modeling chain has a significant impact on future hydro-climatic trajectories. In particular, the combination of climate-and-hydrological-correction procedures may be optimal when both climate biases and hydrological model errors are significant. Moreover, using multiple bias correction methods can strengthen the ensemble of future hydro-climatic conditions. These findings have implications for vulnerability–impact–adaptation studies and underscore the importance of rigorous modeling chain design and sensitivity analysis.

Key words: bias correction, climate change, hydrological scenario production, Senegal River Basin

HIGHLIGHTS

- The choice of bias correction method can significantly impact the resulting hydrological scenarios.
- Removing the biases with a climate-correction procedure, hydrological-correction procedure, or a combination of both also notably influences the hydrological-scenario outcomes.
- Resorting to several bias correction methods can be seen as a factor to strengthen the ensemble of future hydro-climatic conditions.

1. INTRODUCTION

For over a century (IPCC 2021), anthropogenic factors such as global warming and land conversion have altered the Earth's climate to the point where the stationary hypothesis is no longer realistic (Milly *et al.* 2008). Significant shifts in precipitation and evaporation regimes are expected in many parts of the world (Nikulin *et al.* 2012; Knutti & Sedláček 2013), which in turn affect the water cycle and water management (Olmstead 2014).

Water resources system performances are highly dependent on water availability. To address the non-stationary issues imposed by climate changes, many modeling frameworks have been proposed since the 2000s. Those frameworks can be broadly classified into two categories (Füssel 2007): (i) deterministic frameworks (the so-called 'top-down' approach) and (ii) stress-tests (the 'bottom-up' approach).

In top-down approaches, a modeling chain is developed to derive future hydro-climatic conditions and to assess their impacts on water resources systems. In general, the first link of the modeling chain is the climate simulation. For catchment scale studies, the use of a set of downscaled simulations provided by regional circulation models (RCMs) is encouraged as their refined resolution allows for the reflection of hydro-climatic features and basin heterogeneity, which global circulation models (GCMs) cannot provide (Maraun 2016; Giorgi 2019; Lee *et al.* 2019). As highlighted by Bergström *et al.* (2001) and mentioned in Teutschbein & Seibert (2012), the hydrological variables from RCMs (such as runoff) might not be directly used

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due to their inability to capture certain physical feedbacks (such as infiltration and re-evaporation) at the local scale in RCMs. Instead, it is recommended to feed an independent land surface model (LSM) with RCM climate information. The modeling chain typically includes a climate model, an LSM (such as a hydrological model), and a water management model (WMM).

On the other hand, bottom-up approaches aim at improving our understanding of regional and sectoral climate-related vulnerabilities by conducting stress-tests. In this case, future hydro-climatic conditions may be used as stressors to identify the hydro-climatic conditions that lead to system failure. GCM/RCM projections are then used to assess the possibility of system failure due to climate change (Brown & Wilby 2012; Culley *et al.* 2016). Generally speaking, the use of GCM and RCM simulations has become a common practice in most vulnerability, impact, and adaptation (VIA) studies (Brown *et al.* 2015; Giorgi & Gutowski 2015; Enayati *et al.* 2021).

However, both GCM and RCM outputs display systematic errors, failing to reproduce the observed climate's statistics accurately (Boé *et al.* 2007; Giorgi *et al.* 2009; Teutschbein & Seibert 2012) due to differences in their conceptualization, discretization, and assumptions (Knutti & Sedláček 2013). These biases exist in both the historical and projection parts of the simulations, and can propagate across the modeling chain. To address this issue, several methods have been developed since the 2000s (Maraun *et al.* 2010; Johnson & Sharma 2012; Chen *et al.* 2021). Univariate bias correction methods such as linear scaling (Boé *et al.* 2007) adjust a single statistical parameter, such as the mean, while multivariate methods correct statistical parameters while addressing spatial and/or temporal correlations between variables (Vrac & Friederichs 2015; Cannon 2018). Regardless of the method, biases are identified in a reference period and then removed from the historical and projected parts of the simulation, assuming that biases remain constant over time.

Properly removing the bias across a modeling chain is a challenging topic, which can be summarized in two questions. First, how does using different types of bias correction methods affect future trajectories? Second, should we correct the climate simulations before driving a LSM (also known as the 'climate-correction procedure'), or should we feed an LSM with raw climate simulations and then correct the hydrological outputs (also known as the 'hydrological-correction procedure')?

Ghimire *et al.* (2019) delved into the consequences of employing multiple bias correction methods on hydrological outputs (with a climate-correction procedure). However, this investigation was restricted to the historical part of the simulations and did not encompass any frequency-based bias correction methods (which could substantially alter year-to-year variability: Nguyen *et al.* 2016). Chen *et al.* 2021 studied the impacts of adopting either a climate-correction procedure or a hydrological-correction procedure across 12 small to medium watersheds (with the empirical quantile mapping method). Nevertheless, their focus was solely on the historical part of the simulations. Therefore, the existing literature lacks a comprehensive exploration of the sensitivity associated with the bias correction step in generating hydrological scenarios. This gap includes the integration of (i) diverse bias correction methods and (ii) distinct bias correction procedures such as climate and hydrological adjustments, all with a specific focus on the projection part of the simulations.

In this study, we propose to investigate this gap. We designed a framework to evaluate the sensitivity of hydrological scenario production to the bias correction step for a future horizon. In addition to the climate-correction procedure and hydrological-correction procedure, the framework incorporates the climate-and-hydrology correction procedure, which embeds both procedures.

The framework is illustrated using the Senegal River Basin (SRB) as a case study. This basin has experienced significant shift in its precipitation regime since 1940s, and undergoes actually flourishing development. Applying our framework to such a basin will help basin authorities in documenting plausible future hydro-climatic trajectories, an area where the future hydro-climatic trajectories display no clear trend (IPCC 2022). It will also provide to the scientific community a concrete example of how sensitive a modeling chain can be to the bias correction step.

2. FRAMEWORK PRESENTATION

The proposed framework aims at showing how sensitive is the production of hydrological scenarios to the bias correction step using either a climate-correction or a hydrological-correction procedure, or a combination of both.

Figure 1(a) provides an overview of the generic framework. Each panel in the Figure 1(a) represents a specific bias correction method (denoted as X). Within each panel, three cases are defined as follows.

A first case that corresponds to the climate-correction procedure (denoted X_C , and depicted by the green boxes in Figure 1(a)). The bias correction method is applied to climate simulations to provide climate scenarios. The LSM is then fed with these climate scenarios to produce hydrological scenarios.

(a) Generic framework

(b) Application of the framework

Figure 1 | (a) Framework proposed to evaluate the sensitivity of the hydrological scenario production to the bias correction step. The framework consists of establishing n panels, each referring to a specific bias correction method X . Inside each panel, three cases are defined. Green, blue, and orange boxes refer to the climate-correction procedure, hydrological-correction procedure and the climate-and-hydrological-correction procedure, respectively. (b) Application of the generic framework to the Senegal River Basin.

A second case that refers to the hydrological-correction procedure (denoted X_H , and depicted by the blue boxes in Figure 1(a)). The LSM is fed with raw (uncorrected) climate simulations to produce hydrological simulations. The correction method is then applied to these hydrological simulations.

A third case that refers to the climate-and-hydrological-correction procedure (denoted X_{CH} , and depicted by the orange boxes in Figure 1(a)). First, we correct the climate simulations and then feed the LSM with these climate scenarios. Finally, we apply the correction method to the LSM outputs.

The procedures described above are based on certain expectations and assumptions. The climate-correction procedure (X_C) aims to eliminate climate biases, but the errors of the LSM may still persist. The hydrological-correction procedure (X_H)

addresses both climate biases and LSM errors simultaneously, but using uncorrected climate data in the LSM can potentially impact the model's operation (see Section 5.3 for further details). By combining both the climate-correction and hydrological-correction procedures (X_{CH}), we can ensure the removal of climate biases and LSM errors without any potential distortion of the LSM. Finally, the evaluation phase assesses the sensitivity of hydrological scenario generation to the bias correction step.

3. STUDY CASE: THE SRB

3.1. Background

The Senegal River drains a basin shared by four countries: Guinea, Mali, Mauritania and Senegal (Figure 2(a)). The headwaters are located in the Fouta Jalon (Guinea), where the Bafing River runs northward until merging with the Bakoye in Mali, forming the Senegal River. Running north-west, it collects water from the Faleme river before reaching Bakel, a key-point for the water allocation decision in the basin. Downstream of Bakel, incremental inflows are insignificant (Bader *et al.* 2015). So, only the active part of the basin has been modeled, whose corresponding outlet is Bakel (draining an area of 393,754 km²).

The observed annual flow at Bakel is 21.5 ± 8.7 km³ per year (calculated on 1904–2011 using monthly inflow time-series (Bader *et al.* 2015)). The monsoon onset brings the wet season (typically from July to October), which represents 88% of the annual discharge (Figure 2(b)). The dry season follows (from November to June) during which ~12% of the annual flow is discharged. During the 21st century, the SRB experienced shifts between well-distinct dry, wet, and neutral periods (Figure 2(c)) (Bodian 2014; Bader *et al.* 2015; Faye *et al.* 2015; Guilpart *et al.* 2021).

In the 1970s, l'Organisation pour la mise en valeur du fleuve Sénégal (OMSV, the basin authorities) initiated the construction of two major hydraulic infrastructures: the Manantali dam on the Bafing and the Diama dam close to the river mouth. Today, water-related activities in the basin are flourishing. New major infrastructures will support the development of irrigation, navigation and hydropower generation (CSE *et al.* 2011). Also, the storage capacity will increase from 6.5 km³ (today) to

Figure 2 | (a) The Senegal River Basin, boundaries, infrastructures and river network. The basin has been delimited with the help of the ArcGIS model (version 10.4), and the digital elevation model of the SRTM (resolution: 1 arc-second) Werner (2001). (b) Boxplot of monthly inflows at Bakel (the blue line represents the annual cycle). (c) Annual volume of flow at Bakel (the red line represents the ten year moving average). Data come from the actualization of the SRB monograph (Bader *et al.* 2015).

13 and to 27 km³ with the construction of the so-called second generation of dams by 2050 (to reach a total of six dams) and the construction of the third-generation dams by the end of the century (to reach a total of 12 dams).

Due to notable changes in precipitation patterns, ongoing basin development, and the substantial discrepancies in climate models projecting the future hydro-climatic conditions (IPCC 2022), the SRB stands as an ideal case study for implementing the proposed framework.

3.2. Implementation of the framework in the SRB

This study aims to evaluate the sensitivity of hydrological scenario production to the bias correction step. The first step toward achieving this goal is to carefully select the bias correction methods for testing.

The choice of a bias correction method is dependent on the objectives of the study. In earlier studies focused on vulnerability–impact–adaptation, mean-based adjustments and distribution-based adjustments were the most commonly used methods. However, in recent years, frequency-based correction methods have emerged as a viable alternative (Nguyen *et al.* 2016). For the purposes of water management, the long-term persistence of hydrological variables is of particular importance in high storage-capacity systems, which is the case for the SRB.

Also, we propose an application of the general method by involving the three following bias correction methods (Figure 1(b)). Consequently, this provides us with nine distinct cases, comprising the following methods:

1. The Linear Scaling method (LS) (Boé *et al.* 2007): This method focuses on correcting the mean of the simulation. Further details on the algorithm can be found in the Supplementary Material (Section C.1.).
2. Empirical Quantile Mapping method with a scale transformation (EQM-ST) (Piani *et al.* 2010): EQM-ST seeks to adjust the mean and distribution of the simulation at the monthly time-step by defining a sequence of quantiles. Refer to the Supplementary Material (Section C.2.) for more information on the algorithm.
3. Nested Bias Correction method (NBC) (Johnson & Sharma 2012): NBC adjusts the mean, standard deviation, and Lag-1 autocorrelation at both monthly and yearly time steps. Further details on the method and its application can be found in the Supplementary Material (Section C.3.).

Before applying bias correction methods, it is important to discuss how the trend in hydro-climatic variables is handled. In this study, we follow the guidelines provided by Maraun (2016). Precipitation is a major driver of the inflows in the basin, meaning it plays a critical role in determining the amount of water that flows into the river system. The physical processes inherent to West African monsoon are poorly represented by the GCMs (Philippon *et al.* 2010) and by the RCMs (Sylla *et al.* 2016). Indeed, processes involved in precipitation dynamics range from global scale (as sea surface temperature patterns) to cumulus-scale, and significant biases are reported in RCM outputs over the past periods (Akinsanola *et al.* 2015). Because the precipitation processes are still poorly represented, so precipitation trends in simulations might be implausible, and the associated biases are time-dependent. As a result, there are significant biases in the outputs of these models. In particular, the biases in the simulation of precipitation are time-dependent, which means that they change with time. Given the limitations in simulating precipitation, we do not consider the trends in precipitation to be reliable enough for use in bias correction methods. As precipitation is the main driver of the inflows in the basin, we do so when we apply a bias correction method to inflows. However, as the trend in potential evapotranspiration (PET) is mainly driven by the increase of the temperature due to global warming (Ndiaye *et al.* 2021), we consider that trends in PET simulations are more reliable. Therefore, in this study we explicitly conserve the trend in PET by removing it prior to applying a bias correction method, and then adding it back afterward. This helps to ensure that any errors in the simulated PET data are corrected while still preserving the underlying trend in the data.

Please note that the selected Land Surface Model (LSM) requires spatially averaged time-series to run, as explained in Section 3.2.1. When applying a climate-correction procedure, each grid cell of climate simulations is independently corrected, followed by spatial averaging over the basin. On the other hand, when applying a hydrological-correction procedure, the climate simulations are first spatially averaged to feed the LSM. Finally, bias correction methods are applied to LSM outputs. Figure 1(b) illustrates the necessary elements for deriving future hydrological conditions in the SRB, which include a set of climate simulations, selecting an appropriate LSM, and climate and hydrological observations to correct and calibrate the LSM. It is also important to define a reference period and a horizon for the evaluation.

As depicted in Figure 1(b), the following elements are required to derive the future hydrological conditions in the SRB:

1. A set of climate simulations.
2. Selecting an LSM.

3. A set of climate and hydrological observations in order to correct the climate simulations as well as calibrate and validation the LSM.
4. Defining a reference period and a horizon on which the evaluation will be carried out.

3.2.1. The GR2M as the LSM

Since the data are too sparse and incomplete in the SRB to use a distributed hydrological model based on physics, our choice inclines toward a conceptual LSM. Operating at a monthly time-step and already having proven good performances in the SRB (Ardoin-Bardin 2004; Bodian *et al.* 2012; Guilpart *et al.* 2021), we adopted the conceptual hydrological model GR2M (Figure 3) (Mouelhi 2003). Due to its conceptualization, the GR2M is not able to account for dam operations. Thus, the GR2M requires a naturalized time-series of inflows for the calibration/validation step, wherein the effects of dam operations have been removed. The model calibration and validation process are carried out using the differential split-sample test described by Klemeš (1986), along with the three-states Hidden Markov Model classification method developed by Guilpart *et al.* (2021). The Kling–Gupta efficiency (KGE) is used as the objective function for the model. We set the warming-up period for the GR2M model to two years. More information on the calibration and validation procedures can be found in the Supplementary Material (Section A).

3.2.2. Observation data sets

The GR2M requires PET and precipitation (P) data for running. Observed inflows (Q) are also needed for the calibration/validation step. Thus, we constituted our hydro-climatic database with observations (PET, P , and Q) and with climate simulations (PET and P).

We selected (i) the precipitation distributed dataset from the HSM-SIREM database (Boyer *et al.* 2006; Dieulin *et al.* 2019) (covering the 1940–1998 period); and (ii) the PET from the Climate Research Unit database (Harris *et al.* 2020) (covering the period from 1901 to 2018). Naturalized inflows are retrieved from Bader *et al.* (2015) (1903–2012).

3.2.3. The climate simulation dataset

GCMs used to simulate the SRB's climate have a coarse spatial resolution of approximately 200 km, insufficient for capturing the region's strong climatic variability (Faye *et al.* 2015). To obtain a more detailed representation, we used high-resolution RCMs from the CORDEX-Africa project (Giorgi & Gutowski 2015). From the ensemble of CORDEX-Africa climate

Figure 3 | The GR2M hydrological model.

time-step (please refer to Section D (Supplementary Material) for details about its computation). These metrics are also relevant for an advised water allocation policy in the SRB (Espanmanesh & Tilmant 2022).

4.1. *P*, *PET*, and *Q* trajectories in the SRB

Figure 4 presents the hydro-climatic trajectories in the SRB depending on the bias correction method.

The trend of the precipitation simulations ensemble (i.e. the mean of all the simulations) exhibits low values for the whole period (-0.13 mm/y, 1951–2095), leading to a drop of -2.0% of the precipitation rates between the reference period (652 mm/y, 1951–1998) and the future horizon (639 mm/y, 2050–2095). Similar results with LS, EQM-ST and NBC climate scenarios are found with low modification rates (-1.3% , $+1.0\%$, and -2.2% , respectively). This illustrates that climate models display no consensus in the trend of precipitation in the SRB.

Figure 4 | Precipitation, PET, and inflow trajectories in the SRB. The dashed black line refers to the mean of the simulations (55 for *P*, 22 for PET, and 1,210 for *Q*), the continuous black line to the mean of the LS-scenarios, the blue line to the mean of the EQM-ST scenarios, and the red line to the mean of the NBC scenarios. Green lines refer to the observations. The historical part, the projection part and the studied horizon are displayed.

The PET simulation ensemble trend displays higher values for the whole period (+1.8 mm/y), leading to a significant increase (+175 mm/y, or +7.3%) of the PET between the reference period (2,223 mm/y) and the future (2,399 mm/y). This increase is mainly attributed to the increase of temperature, as highlighted by Ndiaye *et al.* (2021). Although the PET is supposed to be explicitly conserved during the bias correction step (see Section 3.2), we note that LS, EQM-ST and NBC climate scenarios display different trend values (+7.6%, +4.9%, and +8.3%, respectively), and the spread is significant with the EQM-ST method. During the correction, we assume a linear trend. This is generally true for simulations forced by the RCP 8.5 scenario, but not for simulations forced by RCP 2.6 and RCP 4.5. Indeed, as stated in these two RCP scenarios, a decrease of the greenhouse gas emissions is assumed during the 21st century, leading to a compression of the temperature increase that impacts the PET trend. Also, in most simulations of RCP 2.6 and RCP 4.5, when the trend is removed in the projection part of the simulations, the residual PET values are triggered, and the association with quantile is disrupted with the EQM-ST method. Consequently, the correction applied to the future horizon becomes excessive, leading to values lower than expected, which impact the trend at the final stage. Here, we highlight the limits of the willingness to explicitly conserve a trend in a bias correction procedure.

Table 2 gives trend values and mean annual volumes of inflow depending on the procedure and the bias correction method. First, we note that the future horizon remains generally dryer than the reference period. The reduction in the river's annual volume is attributed not solely to the slight decline in precipitation rates, but also to the PET increase. Here, we observe that the effects of climate change become evident first in the rise of PET rather than in an alteration of the rainfall pattern.

Second, we note that the mean annual volumes of the reference period are aligned with the observations (19.3 km³/y) with a hydrological-correction procedure, while an underestimation with the climate-correction procedure (around 16.4 km³/y) can be noticed. The underestimation remains on the future horizon, and the climate-correction procedure leads to minimizing the annual volume by 15.4% or 9.8% compared with the hydrological-correction procedure and climate-and-hydrological-correction procedure. This can be attributed the GR2M errors (which are not removed in the climate-correction procedure). A thorough examination of this issue is undertaken in the following sections.

4.2. Statistical evaluation of bias correction procedures for the reference period

In this section, we first focus on the bias in climate simulations and the effectiveness of bias correction methods in eliminating bias over the reference period. Then, we focus on the hydrological scenarios produced through three correction procedures: the climate-, hydrological-, and climate-and-hydrological-correction procedures. This approach allows us to elucidate the potential propagation of bias throughout the modeling chain.

The left panel of Figure 5 illustrates the statistical parameters (the annual mean, standard deviation, and Acf-Lag1) of both the climate simulations and scenarios for the reference period.

The precipitation simulations exhibit a pseudo-Gaussian distribution centered around the mean annual precipitation rate observed. Nevertheless, the standard deviation and Acf-Lag1 of precipitation simulations are underestimated. All PET simulations display a dry bias (i.e. an overestimation of the PET), high standard deviation, and a weak long-term persistence. These characteristics illustrate that climate models generate simulations with a too-strong year-to-year variability compared with the observations.

Generally speaking, the three bias correction methods successfully adjust the statistic of climate simulations they aim at correcting. However, NBC seems to well adjust the standard deviation and the Acf-lag1 of the precipitation simulations.

Table 2 | Trend values over 1951–2095 (first row), mean annual volumes of inflow depending on the procedure, and the bias correction methods for the historical horizon (second row) and the future horizon (third row)

Simulation	Climate-correction			Hydrological-correction			Climate-and-hydrological-correction			
	LS	EQM-ST	NBC	LS	EQM-ST	NBC	LS	EQM-ST	NBC	
Trend [km ³ /y]	-0.016	-0.009	0.01	-0.016	-0.024	-0.53	-0.014	-0.011	0.008	-0.015
Historical An. Vol. [km ³ /y]	19.5	16.4	16.3	16.3	19.3	19.3	19.3	19.3	19.3	19.3
Future An. Vol. [km ³ /y]	17.8	15.4	17.2	14.4	17.0	17.6	17.7	18.2	20.2	17.4

Figure 5 | Mean annual values and the associated standard deviation of the precipitation (first line) and PET (second line) of the raw simulations, the LS-scenarios, the EQM-ST scenarios and NBC scenarios, for the reference period (1953–1998) (left) and the future horizon (right). The third line presents the Acf-Lag1 values. The green stars and lines refer to the observations.

Figure 6 shows the hydrological simulations and scenarios in 2D-scatter plots, along with the Acf-Lag1 values. We note that the hydrological simulations exhibit a distribution pattern around the observations akin to the precipitation’s. This illustrates that precipitation remains the key driver for the inflow simulation with the GR2M. The hydrological scenarios provided by the climate-correction methods (LS_C, EQM_C, and NBC_C) exhibit a significant deviation from the observed statistics, with an

Figure 6 | Annual Acf-Lag1 boxplots for hydrological scenarios and 2D-scatter plots of the hydrological simulations and scenarios according to the two hydrological attributes: (i) the mean annual volume and (ii) the associated standard deviation. The green stars and the green lines refer to the statistics of the observations.

underestimation of the mean annual volume of 15.5%, 16.0% and 15.5%, respectively. Since climate scenarios no longer exhibit biases, the errors are directly associated with the internal errors of the GR2M. A brief examination of this matter has been conducted (see Section B in the Supplementary Material) and underscores that, while the calibration/validation procedure yielded optimal parameters suitable for various hydrological conditions, errors persist, particularly in dry hydro-climatic conditions, causing the GR2M to underestimate inflows. On the other hand, hydrological-correction methods (LS_H , LS_{CH} , EQM_H , EQM_{CH} , NBC_H , and NBC_{CH}) provide scenarios in which the mean annual volumes are well adjusted (aligned with the observations). Also, incorporating a hydrological-correction allows removal of LSM internal errors, thereby surpassing the effectiveness of climate-correction procedures in reducing overall biases.

4.3. Future hydro-climatic conditions in the SRB

In this section, we initially highlight the disparities in climate scenarios stemming from diverse bias correction methods. Subsequently, we shift our focus to hydrological scenarios, illustrating how the panel of future hydrological conditions is influenced by both bias correction methods and correction procedures.

The right panels of Figure 5 depict the statistical parameters of climate simulations and future climate scenarios. Four main messages can be derived from these observations. Concerning mean annual rates, LS and NBC methods can be considered converging, as they provide a nearly equal distribution of precipitation and PET scenarios. However, the EQM-ST method demonstrates a shifted distribution of its PET scenarios, directly linked to how trends are handled during the correction step (Section 4.1). Finally, the NBC method exhibits limitations in transferring persistence from observations to scenarios, evident in the underestimation of Acf-Lag1 in precipitation scenarios (median of 0.48) and the overestimation in PET scenarios (median of 0.59). This last point is discussed in Section 5.1.

Hydrological simulations and scenarios are depicted in 2D-scatter plots in Figure 7, while Table 3 provides the centroid values and range of the scattered plots. Significant differences are evident among the three bias correction methods and the three procedures. Firstly, the centroid values indicate that climate-correction procedures tend to underestimate inflows (-15.4% , -14.9% , and -17.2% when comparing the centroid of LS_C with that of LS_{CH} , the $EQM-ST_C$ centroid with that of $EQM-ST_{CH}$ and the NBC_C centroid with that of NBC_{CH} , respectively). These underestimations are directly linked to

Figure 7 | For the future horizon, annual Acf-Lag1 boxplots are plotted for hydrological scenarios and 2D-scatter plots of the hydrological simulations and scenarios according to the two hydrological attributes: (i) the mean annual volume and (ii) the associated standard deviation. The green stars and the green lines refer to the statistics of the observations.

Table 3 | Centroids, range values of the mean annual volume and range of the associated standard deviation (km^3/y) of the hydrological simulations and the hydrological scenarios for the future horizon

	Simulations	Climate-correction			Hydrological-correction			Climate-and-hydrological-correction		
		LS	EQM-ST	NBC	LS	EQM-ST	NBC	LS	EQM-ST	NBC
Centroid (km^3/y)	17.8	15.4	17.2	14.4	17.0	17.6	17.7	18.2	20.2	17.4
Range An. Vol. (km^3/y)	0.3–52.1	4.1–33.9	5.4–36.2	4.4–29.6	2.9–31.6	5.8–34.3	3.1–36.9	4.1–38.2	6.6–38.5	7.7–32.9
Range Sd An. Vol. (km^3/y)	0.4–36.9	2.7–22.5	4.0–30.5	3.2–22.4	3.3–23.1	3.4–19.9	2.7–23.3	3.7–28.3	4.3–30.3	3.8–24.2

the GR2M error and are proportionally similar to those observed in Section 4.2. The EQM-ST_C and EQM-ST_{CH} scenarios depict wetter hydrological conditions than the LS and NBC methods, primarily due to low PET values associated with how the PET trend is handled during the bias correction step. The differences range from 9.9% to 16.2%. In other words, the GR2M errors are of comparable magnitude to uncertainties induced by how the trend is handled.

Concerning the range of annual volume, no systematic case emerges, i.e. a climate or hydrological procedure does not systematically lead to an enhanced spread of hydrological conditions. Nevertheless, the range varies significantly among the cases, underscoring that extreme scenarios are not uniform across each case.

There are no consistent and systematic features that stand out across the different hydrological scenarios for annual variability. The NBC method effectively adjusts the Acf-Lag1 when a hydrological-correction procedure is involved (NBC_H and NBC_{CH}) but encounters challenges when applied to correction for climate variables (NBC_C).

In light of these findings, policymakers should keep in mind that both the bias correction method and the procedure can significantly influence future hydro-climatic conditions (centroids and the extreme scenarios). This may impact the selection of hydrological scenarios through clustering methods and consequently affect the inputs for impact models, such as a hydro-economic model.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study highlight the sensitivity of hydrological scenario production to the bias correction step. In this section, we discuss the performance of the three bias correction methods used in our analysis and their ability to adjust the targeted statistical parameters. We also examine the implications of using different correction procedures, including climate-correction, hydrological-correction, or a combination of both.

5.1. Efficiency of the three bias correction methods

First, the LS method succeeds in adjusting the statistical parameters it seeks to correct (the mean), when correcting both climatic or hydrological variables. The EQM-ST method displays good results too when correcting hydrological variables. However, if the mean is well adjusted, EQM-ST fails to correct the standard deviation of climate variables. The situation is analogous with the NBC method. When applied to climate variables, the NBC method may struggle to correct the Acf-Lag1 and the standard deviation, even if it corrects successfully the mean (Figure 5). To explain that fact, a deeper analysis of the climate simulations and climate scenarios is required. When looking at each grid cell of the EQM-ST or NBC climate scenarios, we note that the statistical parameters are well corrected (i.e. their values are close to the observed ones over the reference period, with differences under 5%), meaning the correction works well. However, an inconsistency appears when computing the spatial average over the basin: in the simulation, the spatial consistency can be far from the observed one (mainly due to the climate model conceptualization). In that situation, the corrected time-series may display very different trends from one grid cell to another. This leads to mixing very different trends during the computation of the spatial average, which therefore perturbs the annual standard deviation and the Acf-Lag1 of the averaged time-series. This is especially true with the NBC method. During the correction, the NBC completely modifies the year-to-year variability to correct the Acf-Lag1 autocorrelation (by partially taking into account the year-to-year variability of the simulation).

In consequence, we argue that the EQM-ST and NBC methods successfully correct the statistical parameters within their scope at the grid cell scale. However, it does not necessarily lead to a good adjustment of the statistics (the annual standard deviation and the Acf-Lag1) of the spatial averaged time-series. This is especially true when the spatial consistency of the simulation is far from that of the observation, highlighting that the adequacy between the simulations and the observations is of prime importance.

For PET, the spatial consistency of the simulations is very close to the observed one (indeed, future PET values of simulations are mainly driven by the temperatures (Ndiaye *et al.* 2021), which display a very good homogeneous spatial consistency). However, we face another issue. A significant trend can be observed in PET simulations during the 21st century (Figure 4). When dealing with PET, the trend is explicitly conserved through a detrending/add-back step. Also, the Acf-Lag1 adjustment in the NBC algorithm is carried out prior to adding back the trend, leading to a modification (strengthening) of the ACF-Lag1 when the trend is added, explaining the overestimation of the long-term persistence.

Overall, the bias correction methods presented here work well for correcting one time-series of a simulation independently from the others. Nevertheless, if spatial average time-series are required (such as requested by the GR2M), computing a spatial mean can modify and perturb the statistics of the scenarios, which can lead to mistakes in the quantification of climate changes.

5.2. Involving different bias correction methods

The nature of the bias correction method is also of prime importance. When focusing on the future horizon, we can see that the results in scatter plots are slightly different. The difference especially appears for extreme scenarios (dry, wet or with an important inter-annual variability). Depending on the goals of the vulnerability-impact-adaptation study, investigating the relevance of adaptation schemes could depend on the representation of the extreme events (for inundation prevention or drought consequences for example). In this situation, resorting to several bias correction methods could be seen as a way to increase the panel of future hydro-climatic conditions. Also, this is relevant for top-down and bottom-up approaches in which covering the maximum of plausible climate futures is of prime importance. However, frequency-based bias correction

methods completely modify the temporal shape of a simulation, so that the physical meaning inherited from GCMs/RCMs is partly lost. This questions the relevance of using such a method in a deterministic modeling chain.

5.3. Resorting to a climate-correction procedure, to a hydrological-correction procedure or to a climate-and-hydrological-correction procedure?

Involving a climate-correction procedure, a hydrological-correction procedure or a climate-and-hydrological-correction procedure raises the following key points. First, when the bias correction method is applied to climate data, computation issues (like spatial average as explained earlier) may arise, and the LSM error remains. Conversely, when the bias correction method is applied to hydrological data (i.e. hydrological-correction), the LSM is fed with (raw) climate simulations and the climate biases and the LSM error are removed all at once. However, the LSM inner operation can be modified in a such situation, especially if (i) the raw climate values are far from the corrected ones, (ii) if the spatial consistency of the simulation is far from the observed one (especially for physically based and fully distributed models), and (iii) if the LSM internal scheme has non-linear formulas (typically integrating thresholds). For example, the LSM used in this study (the GR2M) displays a production store that responds to a threshold. Feeding the GR2M with a raw climate simulation having a wet bias can lead to a more frequent saturation of a production store, and thus to an imbalance of the internal scheme of the LSM (compared to feeding the GR2M with a climate scenario without bias). By applying both climate-and-hydrological-correction procedures, we take advantage of both procedures, i.e. removing climate biases and LSM errors independently without any modification of the behavior of the internal scheme of the LSM.

The decision on which procedure to use depends on the quantification of LSM errors and the difference between the values of the climate simulations and their corrected values. If the LSM error is negligible, a single climate-correction procedure may be satisfactory. However, if the climate biases are negligible or very low, directly feeding an LSM with climate simulations may be a relevant alternative in order to apply a hydrological-correction procedure.

A hydrological-correction procedure conserves the statistical properties strictly, whereas a climate-correction procedure modifies the statistics. The choice between keeping the hydrological process intact or conserving well-corrected statistical parameters such as the distribution of inflows belongs to the modeler.

If methods such as the NBC algorithm successfully correct the statistics (here the mean, the standard deviation and the temporal persistence) of each grid cell, artifacts may arise when computing the spatial average over the basin (leading to modification of the temporal persistence or variability). Applying a hydrological-correction procedure allows potential issues to be overcome in the spatial coherence inherited from the simulations.

In our case study, the GR2M underestimates the annual volume for dry and neutral hydro-climatic conditions (around -15% and -20% , respectively) even though the calibration/validation procedure was designed to cope with climate changes (please see details on its quantification in Section B, Supplementary Material). This explains why the LS_C , EQM_C and NBC_C hydrological scenarios are systematically drier than the other hydrological scenarios ($\sim 15\%$ over the reference period, and between 2.5% and 17.2% over the future horizon).

PET in climate simulations is overestimated (around ~ 250 mm/y in average). Also, some simulations display important biases and overestimate (up to $+30\%$) or underestimate (up to -35%) the precipitation (visible on the reference period, Figure 5). In this situation, both PET and P have significant biases which surely perturb the operation of the production store (Figure 3).

Here, we show that LSM errors, the climate biases and the spatial inconsistency of the simulations are all factors we must take into account. Mean annual volume, annual variability, and long-term persistence are relevant indicators for water allocation policy design. Therefore, applying both climate-and-hydrological-correction procedures with the NBC method in the SRB is relevant for a modeling chain designed according to the scope of the vulnerability–impact–adaptation study.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This article evaluates the sensitivity of hydrological scenarios to the bias correction step. By taking the SRB as the study case, we show how a climate-correction procedure, a hydrological-correction procedure or a combination of both affects the production of the hydrological scenarios and how future hydro-climatic trajectories are impacted by the choice of the bias correction method. The main conclusions can be listed as follows:

- From a policymaker's perspective, employing multiple bias correction methods could be regarded as a way to enhance the ensemble of future hydro-climatic conditions. This is particularly relevant for vulnerability–impact–adaptation studies that seek to assess the robustness of a system in the face of extreme events.
- In the design of a modeling chain to derive future hydrological conditions from climate simulations, modelers should be mindful that a climate-correction procedure preserves LSM errors, which may be non-negligible in certain instances (approximately 15% of the mean annual volume in our study). On the other hand, a hydrological-correction procedure addresses both climate biases and LSM errors simultaneously. However, utilizing uncorrected climate data in a hydrological-correction procedure can impact the internal scheme of the LSM, particularly for physically based and fully distributed models or those incorporating thresholds. Therefore, the optimal approach may involve combining both correction methods, especially when both climate biases and LSM errors are substantial.
- Special attention should be given to how trends in simulations are managed during a bias correction step, particularly when employing a quantile mapping method. This is crucial to prevent the introduction of additional errors, which, in some cases, can be of a magnitude comparable to the LSM errors, as observed in our study.

This paper has underscored the critical role of the bias correction step in a top-down modeling chain. However, additional analyses are required on various aspects of the methodology, such as focusing on how the internal scheme of a hydrological model can be disrupted in a hydrological procedure. Another avenue for exploration is examining the suitability of frequency-based bias correction methods in mitigating biases in a context of poor adequacy between simulations and observations. These are examples of study directions that warrant further exploration.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data cannot be made publicly available; readers should contact the corresponding author for details.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare there is no conflict.

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